

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT ON STUDENT LEARNING SUCCESS

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the current problem of personality traits – temperament, and its own definition of the concept of "temperament" is given. A retrospective analysis of the scientific contribution of leading scientists in the field of studying the psychological characteristics of temperament is presented. The theory of E. Kretschmer, I. P. Pavlov, and the essence of Sheldon's concept are considered. The conclusion describes the results of the study "Features of the influence of temperament on the success of students' education", and formulates general conclusions on the relevance and significance of the study in practical terms.

Key words: temperament, students, educational process, scientists, personal quality, neuroticism.

Introduction. Our planet is now home to more than 7 billion people. We all differ not only in external, but also in internal features. This diversity is expressed by many factors, one of them is a person's temperament. This fundamental concept is well understood in its semantic meaning, but it is still insufficiently studied in research, despite a large number of scientific papers. After analyzing a number of concepts related to the personal property "temperament", we can give it such a definition.

Temperament is the biological and psychological characteristics of an individual, which gives a characteristic of a person's personality from the side of dynamically developing mental processes in him:

- 1) the strength of mental experiences, their depth or superficiality;
- 2) the speed of mental processes;
- 3) the degree of emotional excitability that gives a person's behavior a peculiar emotional coloring.

Among the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the study of temperament, one can single out Hippocrates, who believed that the state of the body depends mainly on the quantitative ratio of "juices" or liquids present in the body.

I. P. Pavlov– Russian physiologist and psychologist, German philosopher I. Kant, who made a great contribution to the systematization of psychological ideas about temperaments, believed that the natural basis of temperament is individual characteristics of blood. Similar to this point of view is the idea of the Russian educator, anatomist and physician P. F. Lesgaft, who wrote that the basis of temperament manifestations is ultimately the properties of the circulatory system. Widely known are the works of the German psychiatrist E. Kretschmer, which substantiate the idea that differences in the types of body structure (some features of growth, fullness, proportions of body parts) also indicate certain differences in temperament. It is also possible to distinguish such scientists as W. Sheldon, I. P. Pavlov, G. Y. Aizenkovao and others, each of whom considered temperament using different approaches, studying the

variety of processes in the body depending on the type of temperament. Each of these processes has an impact on the life activity of a person.

Features of temperament strongly influence all spheres of human activity, including educational activities in the educational process. The concept of temperament also includes the emotional and strong-willed sides of a person, his behavior and activities. Temperament can be called the link between personality, body and cognitive processes of a person. For a long time, many scientists have found some regularity, which was manifested in the fact that some differences in people's behavior are related to their physiological differences. The researchers tried to group these differences, and came to a general conclusion about how temperament depends on the physiology of the individual. In modern psychology, temperament is understood as a feature of the psyche in terms of dynamic qualities - the intensity and speed of mental processes. Temperament characteristics have a significant impact on students' learning activities in the modern educational environment.

According to I. P. Pavlov, it was possible to note four basic and typical combinations that are formed through four types of higher nervous activity of a person. I. P. Pavlov compared their manifestations in behavior in direct connection with the classification of temperament in antiquity:

1. Sanguine temperament – a strong, balanced, mobile type of nervous system.
2. Phlegmatic temperament-strong, balanced, calm.
3. Choleric temperament-strong, unbalanced, mobile.
4. Melancholic temperament – the weakest and most unbalanced.

In work and study, the role of temperament lies in the influence of certain mental states that are caused by unpleasant situations, factors in the emotional sphere. Temperament determines the influence of various factors that determine the level of emotional stress. There are several indicators that help students study their personality in higher school practice: - the motives for which they entered the university; - the level of educational training; what was the nature of their activities before they entered the university; - how developed are their skills and abilities in independent work; - what are their interests and hobbies; how developed are their abilities- individual characteristics of character – - state of health; compliance of these indicators with the content and requirements for the future profession. In order to identify the above characteristics, it is possible to use methodological tools, data from the observation method, reviewing students' independent works, results of control tasks, testing, tests, exams. Further, on the basis of such research, an individual approach to students is carried out. Difficulties in studying and practical work, preferences for academic disciplines and types of classes are determined, the level of one's activity and personality are objectively assessed, and the degree of one's satisfaction is assessed. In this regard, the relevant question is whether temperament affects the learning outcomes of students in higher educational institutions. This is especially important for students who are thinking about their future life, and most of them are entering higher education institutions. After all, temperament is an innate quality of a person, and it cannot be changed. Based on this, a study was conducted to find out how much this personal quality affects students' learning. The object of the study was to determine the dependence of learning success on the type of temperament of students. The subject of the study: features of the influence of temperament on the speed of learning of 2nd-year SamSMU students. In the course of the research, the following tasks were solved: To solve the set goal, research tasks, the personal questionnaire-

of experimental psychologist G. Eysenck and data on the academic performance of the studied students were used. There were 30 people (20 girls and 10 boys) who wanted to take part in the study out of 2-year students aged 18-19 years. At the first stage of the study, after interviewing the subjects, unreliable results were eliminated using a lie scale. Among the tested students, the results of which were reliable, there were 10 sanguine, 6 choleric, 6 phlegmatic and 8 melancholic. The average score of grades among students of each type of temperament was also calculated: Sanguine - 4.5; Choleric - 4.2; Phlegmatic - 4.5; Melancholic - 4.2.

According to the personal questionnaire of G. Eysenck, students with choleric and melancholic temperaments showed the lowest average ball. Analysis of student performance revealed the following information. The "satisfactory" and "unsatisfactory" grades are most often given to students with these topics. This can be explained by the fact that the melancholic and choleric type of temperament has increased emotional instability and a high level of neuroticism.

Conclusions. So, temperament practically does not change during a person's life, so this fact should be considered when determining the academic load for yourself and choosing any additional education in the form of circles, electives and public assignments. From the above, it can be concluded that the success of students' learning depends on such indicators of temperament as a high level of neuroticism and instability. As a result, each group of representatives of the four temperament types showed rather high average performance scores, with the exception of one important pattern: only choleric and melancholic students had "satisfactory" or lower grades. These temperament types are characterized by a high level of neuroticism and instability. It can be assumed that these indicators significantly affect the ability to successfully learn, but we should also not forget about compliance with the conditions of upbringing and development. In the future, the results of this research work can be considered by teachers, curators, specialists in educational and educational work to improve the educational process, which could be comfortable for all students, regardless of their temperament type. Taking into account such a personal factor as temperament in the work of the above-listed subjects of education can lead to an increase in the level of education and activity of students in extracurricular activities in educational institutions.

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